

MICRO-MECHANICAL MULTIAXIAL FATIGUE MODEL FOR CRACK DENSITY EVOLUTION AND STIFFNESS DEGRADATION

J.A. Glud¹, J.M. Dulieu-Barton², O.T. Thomsen^{1,2} and L.C.T. Overgaard¹

¹Department of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, Aalborg University
Fibigerstraede 16, DK-9220 Aalborg East, Denmark

Email: [jag,ott,lcto}@m-tech.aau.dk](mailto:{jag,ott,lcto}@m-tech.aau.dk), web page: <http://www.m-tech.aau.dk>

²Faculty of Engineering and the Environment, University of Southampton
Highfield, SO17 1BJ Southampton, United Kingdom

Email: [janice,o.thomsen}@soton.ac.uk](mailto:{janice,o.thomsen}@soton.ac.uk), web page: www.southampton.ac.uk/engineering

Keywords: Multiaxial Fatigue, Intralaminar, Fracture Mechanics, Micro Mechanics

ABSTRACT

The current research effort with regard to the development of a micro-mechanical multiaxial fatigue model for use in wind turbine blade applications is presented. The input parameters required for the model are identified and described. Results from a preliminary experimental campaign on a [0/-60/0/60]_s laminate are presented. Micro-mechanical material data are derived from the test results using a novel measurement and post processing technique which allows for fast, accurate and reproducible crack measurements. The micro-mechanical multiaxial fatigue model is based on the GLOB-LOC constitutive framework. GLOB-LOC is benchmarked against the fatigue tests and good agreement between GLOB-LOC and experiments was found, whereas the classical ply discount method was found to give poor results.

1 INTRODUCTION

Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) laminates are used extensively in wind turbine blades. Wind turbine blades are weight critical structures and are subjected to ultra-high cycle fatigue due to their long service life of over 20 years. The fatigue loading experienced by the GFRP laminates is multiaxial and causes strength and stiffness degradation, which leads to a finite lifetime of the blades. The most widely applied design methods in the wind turbine industry make use of phenomenological methods, which require extensive testing from down-scaled laminate coupon to full scale components and, at best, can only be considered valid for the specific laminate. Improving current fatigue design methodologies for laminated GFRP structures will result in more efficient use of the materials and reduce the extensive need for fatigue prototype testing. Both of these possibilities will greatly aid the wind turbine manufacturers in achieving the levelized cost of conventional energy sources.

In the past decade, several new phenomenological fatigue models have been proposed. Among those models can be mentioned [1], [2], [3] and [4]. These are based on the assumptions from [5], where failure of laminated composites is divided into two phenomena namely fibre failure and matrix failure. Therefore, the models try to predict when these failure modes occur and how they affect the overall structure. The same loading variables, which have an influence on the life of metallic structures, have been reported to influence the fatigue life of GFRP, see e.g. [6]. These loading variables include stress ratio, loading history and amplitude. The phenomenological models used for fatigue life prediction take into account the influence of the loading variables by relying on several SN-curves, constant life diagrams (CLD) and damage accumulation rules such as Palmgren-Miner's linear damage hypothesis. When a failure mode is predicted in a given layer of a composite laminate a penalty to the failed layer's stiffness is applied using e.g. the ply discount method. This results in load redistribution between the layers of the laminate. Ultimate structural failure is usually defined using a compliance criteria or by fibre failure. The models are often only validated with a limited amount of experimental

data and only through the quantities of cycles to failure and stiffness degradation and not with actual damage mechanisms occurring in the material. Furthermore confidence in these models is decreased by the fact the models are highly inspired by those used for metallic models, the assumption being the material behaviour is similar. However, metallic structures usually fail due to a single predominant crack, whereas the final failure mode of laminated composites is progressive where many cracks coalesce. A recent extensive review of phenomenological models can be found in [7], where it was shown that some predictions were non-conservative further questioning the general validity of the models.

It is therefore clear that the failure models for composite laminates must be improved so they are more representative of the actual damage mechanisms. The most severe strength and stiffness degradation is observed in tension fatigue, so improving tension fatigue models is currently of most interest. In rough terms the failure sequence of composite laminates subjected to tension-tension fatigue loading can be divided into off-axis matrix cracking in the majority of the fatigue life, followed by delamination and fibre failure [8].

The overall goal of the present research is to develop a micro-mechanical multiaxial fatigue model for predicting the initiation and evolution of off-axis cracks and the stiffness degradation at the structural scale. The structural scale refers to a body with non-uniform stress/strain field e.g. a wind turbine blade. In order for simulations to be feasible an analytical model is required. Several analytical models for accurately predicting the stiffness degradation as function of the off-axis crack state have been proposed (see e.g. [9], [10], [11]) but widely accepted models describing the initiation and evolution of matrix cracks in multidirectional laminates subject to fatigue loadings are yet to be proposed.

The present paper outlines the material input parameters and constitutive framework needed for the multiaxial fatigue model currently under development. The material data required for the model are identified based on a qualitative investigation of the off-axis crack evolution morphology observed in experiments. The required material data is then derived based on results from a preliminary test campaign. Using transilluminated white light imaging along with a novel measurement and post processing method it has been possible to identify the material parameters for the model in a fast, accurate and reproducible manner. A brief description of the constitutive framework used for the model namely the GLOB-LOC model is provided. Stiffness degradation predictions obtained using the GLOB-LOC model are compared to stiffness degradation measurements obtained from the preliminary test campaign. Good agreement is found, which illustrates the potential of developing a multiaxial fatigue model based on micro-mechanics.

2 OFF-AXIS CRACK EVOLUTION MORPHOLOGY

The most common damage mode in GFRP is transverse intralaminar cracks in the individual ply, which lead to through-thickness tunnelling cracks in the matrix of constrained laminated layers and fibre debonds propagating along the fibres. In this work and by other authors the transverse cracks are referred to as off-axis cracks. If the damage state of a GFRP laminate can be defined in terms of off-axis cracks it would be a useful damage parameter since it can be interpreted as a true internal state variable. The evolution of damage in terms of off-axis cracks can roughly be divided into two phenomena, namely initiation and growth of cracks ([12], [13] and [14]). It is possible to quantify when initiation occurs and how the cracks grow by careful examination of images of off-axis cracks acquired for different number of cycles. Examples of such images can be seen in Figure 1, where (a) shows initiation of off-axis and (b) shows growth of the initiated cracks.

Figure 1: Off-axis cracks in a $[0/-60/0/60]_s$ laminate. (a) initiation of off-axis cracks at 1000 cycles and (b) growth of individual off-axis cracks at 2600 cycles.

If the initiation site of a crack is at least three times the layer thickness away from other cracks, the number of cycles to initiation of the crack can be used as a basis for an independent fatigue strength measurement [14]. In this way, it is possible to obtain many fatigue strength measurements from a single specimen and hence construct a reliable SN-curve. Furthermore, a tunnelling off-axis crack can be regarded as isolated if the crack front is sufficiently far away (three times the layer thickness) from neighbouring cracks and three times the layer thickness long. Thus it is possible to derive Paris-law parameters for the material by measuring the crack growth rate for isolated cracks at different stress levels. Usually several isolated cracks are observed per tested specimen and several independent measurements for the Paris-law are obtained. The SN-curve and Paris-Law constitute the fatigue material data needed as input for the model.

As the crack density increases, the cracks start to interact with each other. The cracks interact through a shielding effect such that interacting cracks do not open as much as isolated cracks. This means that the energy release rate in the crack front is decreased and cracks are therefore arrested from further growth. This explains why crack density evolution curves tend to saturate at a certain value with constant amplitude loading. Based on the crack evolution morphology it can therefore be concluded that for an evolution model to realistically describe the physics three phenomena have to be included namely, initiation, growth and shielding of cracks.

3 MATERIALS, SPECIMEN PREPARATION AND TEST METHODOLOGY

To obtain material data and benchmark results for the micro-mechanical multiaxial fatigue model, a novel measurement and post processing method were developed [15]. The method uses in-situ transilluminated white light imaging to detect off-axis cracks and digital image processing to count the cracks and is referred to in the following as ACC (Automated Crack Counting). The test laminate was 4.3 mm thick with a $[0/-60/0/60]_s$ layup. The laminate was produced using hand lay-up with non-crimp E-glass UD fibre fabrics and impregnated with epoxy using vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding (VARTM). The specimens were cut out from the laminate plate using water jet cutting. The specimens were tested in static loading and fatigue loading. Three different stress amplitudes (113 MPa, 80 MPa and 63 MPa) and a stress ratio equal to $R = 0.1$ were used for the fatigue tests. A 100 kN Instron servo hydraulic test machine applied the fatigue loading; lock-in DIC [16] and an extensometer were used to obtain the stiffness degradation. A photograph of the experimental setup is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Experimental setup for detecting and monitoring stiffness degradation and off-axis cracks.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

ACC counts each individual crack and saves the position of the crack endpoints for all cracks. The method has been validated and is shown to provide accurate and reproducible results. Figure 3(a) shows a comparison of off-axis cracks seen by the digital camera and (b) off-axis cracks counted by ACC. As can be seen virtually all cracks are counted in their full length.

Figure 3: (a) Motion and deformation compensated image of off-axis cracks in the laminate and (b) off-axis cracks counted by the experimental assessment method.

Using ACC it is possible to extract the material data for the multiaxial fatigue model by e.g. detecting initiation of isolated cracks and tracking isolated cracks over several cycles. Figure 4(a) shows SN-data obtained from detection of isolated crack initiations and Figure 4(b) shows the crack growth rate as function of total energy release rate of the isolated crack. Both curves are fitted using a power law. The power law used for fitting and the determined power law parameters are given in Table 1: Determined power law parameters for SN-curve and crack growth rate. Table 1. The SN power law has been chosen as the Basquin relationship and the Paris' law is based on the sum of mode 1 and mode 2 energy release rate as chosen in [14].

Figure 4: Experimental data obtained for (a) SN-data and (b) crack growth rate results.

SN curve		Paris' Law	
$S = S_0 N^k$		$CGR = D \cdot (G_I + G_{II})^n$	
$S_0 = 74.3^{+1.9}_{-1.8}$	$k = -0.0458 \pm 0.0047$	$D = 0.0437^{+0.039}_{-0.0206}$	$n = 1.69 \pm 0.31$

Table 1: Determined power law parameters for SN-curve and crack growth rate. Confidence level for bounds on determined parameters are 95%.

From Figure 4(a) it is seen that initiation results have only been obtained for low cycle fatigue. Hence more tests at stress amplitude lower than 63 MPa are required to derive an SN-curve based on high cycle data as well. In Figure 5 crack density as function of fatigue cycles are shown for (a) the thick layer and (b) the thin layer of the laminate. The crack density is defined as the total crack surface area divided by volume of the damaged measuring volume [14].

Figure 5: Crack density as function of cycles for three different stress amplitudes. Crack density evolution is shown for (a) thick layer and (b) thin layer.

From Figure 5 it is clearly seen that the crack density evolution rate increases when the amplitude of the applied loading is increased. This phenomenon can be explained by the crack morphology; when

the stress is increased cracks initiate earlier and more cracks initiate. Furthermore when a crack has initiated it grows faster according to the crack growth rate results. The combined result is an increased crack density evolution rate. Moreover Figure 5 shows that the value at which the crack density saturates increases with increasing load. This is explained by the shielding effect. When the stress is increased the cracks have to be located closer to each other to provide the necessary shielding effect so new cracks cannot be formed and those already formed can be arrested.

5 CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

Evolution and initiation of off-axis cracks are localised damage occurring at the microscopic scale. An efficient multi-scale approach is a necessity if damage at the structural scale is to be simulated, which is the goal of the present research. Many efforts have been devoted to develop models describing the correlation between elastic properties of the laminate at macro-scale and crack density (see e.g. [9], [17], [18], [10]). The GLOB-LOC model ([9], [17]) was chosen as damage model for the present fatigue model. The GLOB-LOC model is based on the micromechanical theorem, which states that the global laminate strains can be computed by averaging the strains over the volume of each layer. Using the divergence theorem it can be shown that this is equal to averaging the displacements of all surfaces in the given layer. Using the iso-strain condition of laminate layers at the global scale, the problem is reduced to determining the average crack opening displacement (COD) and average crack sliding displacement (CSD) of the off-axis crack faces. [9] and [17] derived master curves for average COD and CSD respectively using unit-cell FE-models. The master curves were normalised with respect to the classical lamination theory (CLT) stress in the undamaged layers. The only sensitive parameters were the thickness of the cracked layer (t_{90}), thickness of adjacent laminates (t_s), stiffness of cracked layer (E_2) and stiffness of adjacent sublaminates orthogonal to the orientation of the crack (E_x^s). The stiffness values of adjacent sublaminates are computed using CLT for each sublaminates and then E_x^s is defined as the average of these stiffness values. The mastercurve for COD is given by the following expressions:

$$u_{1an}^0 = 0.52 + \left(0.3075 + 0.1652 \left(\frac{t_{90} - 2t_s}{2t_s} \right) \right) \left(\frac{E_2}{E_x^s} \right)^{n_1} \quad (1)$$

$$n_1 = 0.030667 \left(\frac{t_{90}}{2t_s} \right)^2 - 0.0626 \left(\frac{t_{90}}{2t_s} \right) + 0.7037 \quad (2)$$

As seen from equations (1) and (2) the predicted COD is nonlinear in the mentioned parameters. The GLOB-LOC is computationally efficient for large scale structures since it is based on the CLT framework. [9] and [17] validated the stiffness degradation predictions with experimental data and found good agreement between model and experimental results. However, the comparison to experimental test data was only carried out for quasi-static tests.

6 APPLICATION TO EXPERIMENTAL DATA

A benchmark of the stiffness degradation prediction from the GLOB-LOC model using results from the fatigue tests was carried out to assess the performance of the model before extending it with a crack evolution model. A comparison of the model and stiffness degradation measurements obtained using lock-in DIC and extensometer is seen in Figure 6. The only input required for the GLOB-LOC model is layup, ply properties (E_1 , E_2 , G_{12} and ν_{12}) and crack density measurements. The stiffness degradation predicted from the ply discount method is also shown.

Figure 6: Comparison between stiffness degradation prediction using GLOB-LOC and measured stiffness degradation using extensometer and Lock-in DIC [16].

From Figure 6 it is clearly seen that the GLOB-LOC model and the experimental results agree well. The ply discount method used by many phenomenological methods predicts too severe stiffness degradation and may be one explanation for the sometimes poor predictions offered by such models.

7 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

The constituents needed for a micro-mechanical multiaxial fatigue model have been identified. ACC allowed for fast, accurate and reproducible derivation of material data for the model. A benchmark of the chosen constitutive framework on fatigue results has been carried out and the model was found to perform well. The upcoming research work will focus on defining a suitable parameterisation of the off-axis crack evolution and combine the three identified evolution phenomena, namely initiation, growth and shielding of cracks, into a single micromechanical multiaxial fatigue model.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work presented was conducted as a part of a Ph.D. project at the Department of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, Aalborg University, Denmark. The project has received sponsorship from the Danish Agency for Science, Technology and Innovation. The support received is gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

- [1] Mahmood M. Shokrieh and Larry B. Lessard, "Progressive Fatigue Damage Modeling of Composite Materials, Part I: Modeling", *Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 34, no. 13, pp. 1056-1080, jul 2000. [Online]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/002199830003401301>
- [2] V. A. Passipoularidis, T. P. Philippidis, and P. Brondsted, "Fatigue life prediction in composites using progressive damage modelling under block and spectrum loading", *International Journal of Fatigue*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 132-144, feb 2011. [Online]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2010.07.011>
- [3] X. S. Sun et al., "A multi-axial fatigue model for fiber-reinforced composite laminates based on Puck's criterion", *Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 449-469, feb 2012. [Online]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0021998311418701>
- [4] Ciaran R. Kennedy, Conchúr M. Ó. Brádaigh, and Sean B. Leen, "A multiaxial fatigue damage

- model for fibre reinforced polymer composites", *Composite Structures*, vol. 106, pp. 201-210, dec 2013. [Online]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2013.05.024>
- [5] Z. Hashin and A. Rotem, "A Fatigue Failure Criterion for Fiber Reinforced Materials", *Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 448-464, oct 1973. [Online]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/002199837300700404>
- [6] Rogier Nijssen, "Optidat - database reference document", Knowledge Centre WMC, Kluisgat 5 1771 MV Wieringerwerf, the Netherlands, Tech. rep. jun 2006.
- [7] Marino Quaresimin, Luca Susmel, and Ramesh Talreja, "Fatigue behaviour and life assessment of composite laminates under multiaxial loadings", *International Journal of Fatigue*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 2-16, jan 2010. [Online]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2009.02.012>
- [8] Jamison and D. Russell, *Characterization and analysis of damage mechanisms in tension-tension fatigue of graphite/epoxy laminates.*, Astm, Ed.: ASTM International, jan 1984, vol. 1.
- [9] P. Lundmark and J. Varna, "Constitutive Relationships for Laminates with Ply Cracks in In-plane Loading", *International Journal of Damage Mechanics*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 235-259, jul 2005. [Online]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1056789505050355>
- [10] P. A. Carraro and M. Quaresimin, "A stiffness degradation model for cracked multidirectional laminates with cracks in multiple layers", *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, vol. 58, pp. 34-51, apr 2015. [Online]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2014.12.016>
- [11] Chandra V. Singh and Ramesh Talreja, "A synergistic damage mechanics approach for composite laminates with matrix cracks in multiple orientations", *Mechanics of Materials*, vol. 41, no. 8, pp. 954-968, aug 2009. [Online]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.mechmat.2009.02.008>
- [12] M. C. Lafarie-Frenot and C. Hénaff-Gardin, "Formation and growth of 90° ply fatigue cracks in carbon/epoxy laminates", *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 40, no. 3, pp. 307-324, jan 1991. [Online]. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0266-3538\(91\)90087-6](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0266-3538(91)90087-6)
- [13] J. Tong, F. J. Guild, S. L. Ogin, and P. A. Smith, "On matrix crack growth in quasi-isotropic laminates—I. Experimental investigation", *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 57, no. 11, pp. 1527-1535, jan 1997. [Online]. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0266-3538\(97\)00080-8](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0266-3538(97)00080-8)
- [14] M. Quaresimin et al., "Damage evolution under cyclic multiaxial stress state: A comparative analysis between glass/epoxy laminates and tubes", *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 61, pp. 282-290, may 2014. [Online]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2014.01.056>
- [15] J.A. Glud, O.T., Dulieu-Barton, J. Thomsen, and L.C.T. Overgaard, "Intralaminar fatigue characterisation of GFRP laminate using lock-in DIC and TSA for use in micro-mechanics based multiaxial fatigue model.", in *7th International Conference on Composites Testing and Model Identification*, Madrid, 2015.
- [16] R. K. Fruehmann, J. M. Dulieu-Barton, S. Quinn, and J. P. Tyler, "The use of a lock-in amplifier to apply digital image correlation to cyclically loaded components", *Optics and Lasers in Engineering*, vol. 68, pp. 149-159, may 2015. [Online]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.optlaseng.2014.12.021>
- [17] Peter Lundmark and Janis Varna, "Crack face sliding effect on stiffness of laminates with ply cracks", *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 66, no. 10, pp. 1444-1454, aug 2006. [Online]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2005.08.016>
- [18] Chandra V. Singh and Ramesh Talreja, "Evolution of ply cracks in multidirectional composite laminates", *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, vol. 47, no. 10, pp. 1338-1349, may 2010. [Online]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2010.01.016>